

A Prospective Study of Perioperative Cardiopulmonary Complications in Cigarette Smokers Undergoing Major Surgery under General Anaesthesia

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Cigarette smoking remains a global health concern, with significant implications for perioperative outcomes.**Methods:** This prospective study aimed to investigate the impact of smoking on perioperative cardiopulmonary complications in patients undergoing major surgery under general anesthesia. Demographic characteristics, including age distribution and ASA grades, were recorded. Perioperative adverse events, such as heart rate changes during intubation, cough severity, oxygen desaturation, and bronchospasm, were meticulously monitored from induction to post-anesthesia care unit discharge.**Results:** We enrolled 120 patients, including 60 smokers and 60 non-smokers, and assessed demographic characteristics, ASA grades, and perioperative adverse events. Smokers exhibited a higher incidence of adverse events, including elevated heart rates during intubation, severe coughing, bronchospasm, and lower oxygen saturation levels post-extubation. Longer smoking duration exacerbated these risks.**Conclusion:** These findings underscore the importance of tailored perioperative management strategies for smokers, including smoking cessation interventions and preoperative respiratory optimization, to mitigate complications and improve outcomes. Despite limitations, this study provides valuable insights into perioperative risks associated with smoking and highlights the need for further research in this area.**Keywords:** Smoking, Cardiopulmonary, Perioperative Risk, General Anesthesia.

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Introduction

Cigarette smoking remains a prevalent global health issue, contributing significantly to morbidity and mortality through its well-documented effects on various organ systems. Tobacco smoking, a long-established practice, involves inhaling smoke that contains active substances entering the bloodstream through the lungs. [1] Nicotine, the primary component, attaches to brain receptors, leading to dopamine release and reinforcing dependence. [2]

Among the numerous health risks associated with smoking, its impact on perioperative outcomes, particularly in patients undergoing major surgery under general anesthesia, is of paramount concern. Smokers are at an increased risk of developing cardiopulmonary complications during the perioperative period due to the pathophysiological changes induced by chronic tobacco use, including impaired respiratory function, increased airway reactivity, and compromised cardiovascular health. [3]

Research indicates that smokers who quit shortly before surgery tend to have a higher rate of

postoperative purulent sputum compared to non-smokers. [4-6] Both active and passive smokers are more prone to experiencing complications during the induction of anesthesia. [7] They often display increased heart rates and neuroendocrine responses after tracheal intubation, which raises the risk of ischemic heart disease. Additionally, smokers face a greater likelihood of respiratory complications, wound infections, and lower arterial oxygen saturation following surgery. [8-10]

Understanding the specific risks and mechanisms by which smoking exacerbates perioperative cardiopulmonary complications is crucial for developing targeted strategies to mitigate these adverse outcomes. Despite advances in surgical techniques and anesthetic management, cigarette smokers continue to experience higher rates of perioperative complications, which can lead to extended hospital stays, increased healthcare costs, and higher postoperative morbidity and mortality. This research study aims to systematically investigate the incidence, nature, and determinants of cardiopulmonary complications in cigarette

smokers undergoing major surgery under general anesthesia. By examining a comprehensive cohort of surgical patients, this study seeks to elucidate the correlation between smoking status and perioperative outcomes, identify predictive factors for complications, and propose evidence-based recommendations for preoperative assessment and perioperative management.

Materials and Methods

This prospective study investigated perioperative cardiopulmonary complications in smokers and non-smokers undergoing major surgery under general anesthesia. We enrolled 120 patients: 60 smokers and 60 non-smokers. Inclusion criteria included ASA 1 and 2 patients, smokers who smoked 10+ cigarettes daily for at least five years, and those scheduled for major elective surgery under general anesthesia. "Smokers" were those actively smoking at enrollment, while "non-smokers" had never smoked. Exclusion criteria were ASA status 3 and above, acute emergency surgeries, and patients with hypothermia or shivering.

Ethical clearance was obtained and informed consent was secured from each participant, ensuring their understanding and voluntary participation. Patients were assured that their decision to participate would not impact their medical care.

We calculated the sample size based on a study that focusing on heart rate as the outcome variable.¹¹ Using standard deviation, desired power, statistical significance level, and effect size, we determined a minimum sample size of 48 per group. However, we selected 60 participants per group for adequate representation.

After under-going pre-anesthetic evaluations patients fasted for eight hours before surgery and were pre-medicated. In the operating room, we recorded baseline heart rate, blood pressure, and arterial oxygen saturation, and established intravenous access. Pre-oxygenation was performed, and anesthesia was induced with medications including glycopyrrolate, ondansetron, fentanyl, and propofol, followed by tracheal intubation.

We monitored arterial oxygen desaturation ($SpO_2 < 92\%$), laryngospasm, heart rate increase during intubation, bronchospasm, and oral secretion severity from induction to post-anesthesia care unit discharge. Severe coughing, reintubation, naloxone administration, and pulmonary edema incidence were also recorded.

We conducted statistical analysis using Microsoft Excel and SPSS Statistics 26.0. Continuous variables were analyzed using the Student's t-test or Mann-Whitney U test, and categorical variables

were examined using chi-squared tests. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Age Distribution: In the 25–35 age range, there were five smokers (8.3%) and 27 non-smokers (28.3%). For the 35–45 age group, there were 26 smokers (43.3%) and 21 non-smokers (23.3%). In the 45–55 age range, there were 21 smokers (35%) and nine non-smokers (15%). In the 55–65 age group, there were six smokers (10%) and seven non-smokers (6.7%). For the >65 age category, there were two smokers (3.3%) and three non-smokers (5%). The mean age of smokers was approximately 41 years ($SD = 8.1$), and for non-smokers, it was approximately 35 years ($SD = 9.5$). The age distribution differed significantly between groups ($p = 0.028$). (Table 1)

ASA Grades and Oral Secretions at Recovery: Both groups had similar distributions, with 85% in ASA Grade I and 15% in ASA Grade II. There was no significant difference in ASA grade distribution ($p = .997$).

Smokers had a higher prevalence of moderate to high-grade oral secretions compared to non-smokers. Grade 1 secretions were observed in 20% of smokers and 90% of non-smokers. Grade 2 secretions were seen in 65% of smokers and 10% of non-smokers. Grade 3 secretions were found in 15% of smokers, with none in non-smokers. No Grade 4 secretions were observed in either group. (Table 2)

Perioperative Adverse Events: Table 3 indicates a higher incidence of perioperative adverse events among smokers. Severe cough was reported in 31.7% of smokers and 10% of non-smokers. Oxygen desaturation occurred in 16.7% of smokers and 5% of non-smokers. Bronchospasm was seen in 11.7% of smokers and 5% of non-smokers. Laryngospasm was reported in 3.3% each among smokers and non-smokers. No reintubation, naloxone usage, or pulmonary edema occurred in either group. (Table 3)

Smoking Duration and Adverse Events: Among smokers with 5–9 years of smoking, severe cough was seen in 20.6% and 46.1% of those smoking for 10+ years, 8.8% with 5–9 years of smoking experienced oxygen desaturation, while 26.9% of those smoking for 10+ years did. Bronchospasm and laryngospasm followed similar patterns, with higher rates in long-term smokers. Significant differences were noted for severe cough, oxygen desaturation and bronchospasm. (Table 4)

Heart Rate Increase During Intubation: 46.7% of non-smokers had a heart rate increase of >10 bpm during intubation, while none of the 5–9 years smokers did. For an increase >20 bpm, 50% of

non-smokers and 21.7% of smokers experienced this. Among smokers, 23.6% with 5–9 years and 19.2% with 10+ years showed this increase. For an increase >30 bpm, 3.3% of non-smokers and 73.3% of smokers experienced this. Specifically, 70.6% of 5–9 years smokers and 76.9% of 10+ years

smokers had this increase. No non-smokers had an increase >40 bpm, but 5% of smokers did, with 5.8% in the 5–9 years group and 3.9% in the 10+ years group. Smokers, especially long-term smokers, had more pronounced heart rate responses to intubation compared to non-smokers.

Table 1: Age Distribution of Smokers and Non-smokers

Age Range (in years)	Smokers N (%)	Non-Smokers N (%)
25–35	5 (8.3%)	27 (45%)
35–45	26 (43.3%)	14 (23.3%)
45–55	21 (35%)	9 (15%)
55–65	6 (10%)	7 (11.7%)
>65	2 (3.3%)	3 (5%)
Mean (SD)	41 (8.1)	35 (9.5)

Table 2: ASA Grade Distribution and Oral Secretions at Recovery, Comparing Smokers and Non-smokers

		Number of Smokers	Percentage	Number of Non-smokers	Percentage
ASA Grade	Grade 1	52	87	52	87
	Grade 2	8	13	8	13
Oral Secretions	Grade 1	12	20	54	90
	Grade 2	39	65	6	10
	Grade 3	9	15	0	0
	Grade 4	0	0	0	0

Table 3: Perioperative Adverse Events in study subjects

Events	No. of Smokers	Percentage	No. of Non-smokers	Percentage	p-value
Severe cough	19	31.7	6	10	0.021
Oxygen desaturation	10	16.7	3	5	<0.001
Laryngospasm	2	3.3	2	3.3	0.997
Bronchospasm	7	11.7	3	5	<0.001
Total	38	63.3	14	23.3	

Table 4: Perioperative Adverse Events vs Years of Smoking

Event	Smokers for 5–9 Years	Percentage	Smokers for ≥ 10 Years	Percentage	p-value
Severe cough	7	20.6	12	46.1	0.032
Oxygen desaturation	3	8.8	7	26.9	0.028
Laryngospasm	1	2.9	1	3.8	0.727
Bronchospasm	2	5.9	5	19.2	0.012
Total	13		25		

Table 5: Heart Rate Increase during Intubation

Heart Rate Increase (bpm)	Smokers (5–9 years)		Smokers (10+ years)		Non-Smokers	
>10	0	0%	0	0%	28	46.7%
>20	8	23.6%	5	19.2%	30	50%
>30	24	70.6%	20	76.9%	2	3.3%
>40	2	5.8%	1	3.9%	0	0%

Discussion

The aim of this investigation was to contrast the cardiopulmonary effects during surgery between smokers and non-smokers. The demographic analysis revealed a notable age difference between the two groups, with smokers being predominantly in the 35–45 age bracket.

However, their ASA grades were comparable, indicating a well-matched patient demographic for precise outcome comparison. These findings align with previous studies suggesting similar age distributions and ASA grading between smokers and non-smokers. [12] Our study found that smokers experienced a significantly higher increase in heart rate compared to non-smokers during intubation, consistent with prior research indicating

a heightened sympathetic response in smokers. This effect is likely due to nicotine and respiratory system sensitivity. Given the implications for individuals at risk for ischemic heart disease, anesthesia administration should consider smoking status, with elevated heart rate serving as a crucial indicator of the body's response. [13-15] Chronic cough, a common postoperative issue for smokers, was found to occur at a substantially higher rate among smokers compared to non-smokers. This correlates with previous studies linking smoking to increased respiratory difficulties post-surgery. The hyperactive cough reflex in chronic smokers may stem from bronchial epithelium sensitivity and decreased ciliary function, underscoring the importance of mitigating postoperative cough in this population. [16,17]

Smokers also exhibited worse oxygen desaturation throughout the perioperative period, consistent with previous research indicating a higher prevalence of oxygen deficiency among smokers. This may be attributed to long-term smoking's negative impact on pulmonary function, necessitating continuous monitoring and proactive measures to prevent hypoxemia-related complications.

The study highlighted a higher incidence of bronchospasm among smokers compared to non-smokers, emphasizing the need for vigilant identification and management of this complication in smokers. The association between longer smoking duration and increased perioperative complications underscores the cumulative effects of chronic smoking on the respiratory system, warranting tailored management strategies for smokers based on their smoking history. [18]

In summary, our study sheds light on the heightened perioperative cardiopulmonary complications in smokers compared to non-smokers. Longer smoking duration exacerbates these risks, emphasizing the importance of tailored perioperative management strategies considering smoking status and duration. Smoking cessation interventions and preoperative respiratory optimization should be prioritized to reduce complications and improve outcomes for smokers undergoing surgery.

The study had a few limitations. Firstly, despite efforts to balance smoker and non-smoker groups, there was an observed age difference, which could introduce confounding variables affecting the attribution of perioperative complications solely to smoking. Challenges in managing patient exclusions for surgeries exceeding three hours may have introduced selection bias, and the lack of specificity regarding the number of excluded patients could impact the study's representativeness.

Conclusion

In our study examining perioperative cardiopulmonary complications among smokers and non-smokers undergoing elective surgery, smokers demonstrated significantly higher risks of adverse events, including elevated heart rates during intubation, severe coughing, bronchospasm, and lower oxygen saturation levels post-extubation. Long-term smokers faced even greater risks. Our study highlights the importance of these interventions for enhancing the safety and well-being of smokers undergoing surgery, emphasizing the need for further research to explore long-term impacts and patient satisfaction with these approaches.

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